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Human Resource Diversity and Organisational Outcomes in Akwa Ibom State Secondary Education Board, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined the influence of human resource diversity (HRD) on organisational outcomes within the State Secondary Education Board in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Specifically, it assessed how workforce diversity across gender, age, ethnicity, and educational qualifications relates to job satisfaction, retention intention, and perceived service quality. Anchored on social identity, equity, and cognitive diversity theories, the study employed a quantitative correlation survey design. A stratified random sample of 140 staff members participated, with data collected via structured questionnaires and analysed using descriptive statistics, Pearson's correlation, and multiple regression techniques. The results revealed generally positive perceptions of organisational outcomes, with service quality receiving the highest ratings. However, regression analyses showed no statistically significant relationship between the diversity dimensions and the outcomes measured. These findings suggest that while demographic diversity is present, it does not independently predict job satisfaction, retention, or service effectiveness in the context studied. The study concludes that non-demographic factors may play a more influential role in shaping staff experiences and recommends a broader human resource strategy that integrates inclusive leadership, recognition systems, and organisational climate assessments. This research contributes context-specific

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evidence to Nigeria's public sector diversity discourse and highlights the need for more nuanced approaches to diversity management in educational administration.

Keywords: human resource diversity, job satisfaction, retention, service quality, education board, Akwa Ibom State.

1.1 Introduction

Education is a critical driver of national development, and the quality of secondary education in Nigeria largely depends on the effectiveness of its human resources. State education boards, such as the State Secondary Education Board in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, play a central role in staffing, training, and managing teachers. Despite their importance, little empirical research has investigated how human resource diversity (HRD) in terms of gender, age, ethnicity, and qualifications impacts organisational outcomes like job satisfaction, teacher retention, and service delivery in this context.

Studies across Nigeria highlight the significance of diversity and organisational practices on educational outcomes. In Osun State, Odediji, Bamikole, Afolabi, and Ekundayo (2022) found that teacher job satisfaction, especially tied to recognition and promotion, is significantly correlated with job performance (Odediji et al., 2022). Similarly, Ijiwole, Olawale, and Adebayo (2019) reported that lower-than-expected job satisfaction among secondary school teachers in Osun State adversely affected their performance (Ijiwole et al., 2019). Meanwhile, Obasi and Igbudu (2021) documented strategic diversity-management practices among school administrators in Rivers State, linking workforce heterogeneity to improved school administration (Obasi & Igbudu, 2021). These findings suggest that diversity-aware human resource management contributes positively to teaching outcomes and institutional effectiveness.

Leadership style is another critical organisational factor influencing teacher satisfaction and retention. In Lagos State, democratic leadership has been shown to yield higher levels of teacher satisfaction compared to authoritarian and laissez-faire approaches (Angwaomaodoko, 2023). Similarly, Sanni, Aransi, Esan, and Ayodele (2024) found that supportive leadership, coupled with job satisfaction and engagement, significantly enhanced teacher productivity in Osun State (Sanni et al., 2024). These studies underscore the importance of inclusive leadership and diverse workforce management for favourable organisational outcomes in education.

Despite this body of evidence, research has not sufficiently addressed how HRD affects organisational outcomes within a state-level secondary education board, particularly in Uyo. The existing literature predominantly focuses on school-level practices or specific states like Rivers and Osun. The extent to which diversity dimensions (gender, ethnicity, age, and educational qualifications) drive outcomes such as satisfaction, retention, and service quality under a centralised administrative body remains scarcely investigated.

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1.2 Problem Statement

There is currently a lack of empirical data on the HR diversity profile at the State Secondary Education Board in Uyo and how it correlates with organisational outcomes. This limits opportunities for evidence-based strategies to enhance staff morale, retention, and service delivery.

1.3 Research Objectives

This study seeks to address this gap by:

- i. Profiling HR diversity (gender, ethnicity, age, qualifications) among Board staff.
- ii. Measuring key organisational outcomes: job satisfaction, turnover intention, teacher retention, and perceived service quality.
- iii. Examining the relationships between HRD dimensions and these outcomes.

1.4 Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

- i. What is the demographic profile of staff in terms of gender, age, ethnicity, and educational qualifications within the State Secondary Education Board in Uyo?
- ii. What are the levels of job satisfaction, retention intention, and perceived service quality among staff of the State Secondary Education Board in Uyo?
- iii. To what extent do gender, age, ethnicity, and qualification levels predict job satisfaction, retention intention, and perceived service quality among Board staff?

1.5 Significance of the Study

By focusing on the Uyo State Education Board, this study will generate context-specific insights into how HRD drives organisational effectiveness in state-level secondary education administration. These findings will inform policy and practice in Akwa Ibom State and similar Nigerian contexts.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Theoretical Foundations

2.1.1 Diversity Management and Organizational Justice

Diversity management (DM) refers to organisational efforts that proactively value and support workforce diversity, leading to beneficial outcomes like job satisfaction and employee engagement (Mansoor et al., 2021). Social identity theory suggests that employees categorise themselves into in-groups and out-groups, impacting attachment and potential biases, which effective DM can mitigate (Tajfel, 1979; Oakes et al., 2021). Equity or organisational justice theory complements this by emphasising fair treatment and impartial reward systems, which support diverse populations by reinforcing trust and reducing turnover intentions (Ashforth & Mael, 1989; Mansoor et al., 2021).

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2.1.2 Social Identity and Equity Theories

Social identity theory (Tajfel & Turner, 1979) highlights dynamics of in-group favouritism that may marginalise diverse staff. Diversity management cultivates better social identities by signalling inclusion. Equity theory, which was grounded in justice and fairness principles (Greenberg, 1987), suggests diversity management (DM) fosters perceptions of procedural and distributive justice, linked to increased organisational commitment and decreased turnover (Mansoor et al., 2021).

2.1.3 Cognitive Diversity and Innovation

The cognitive diversity hypothesis holds that diverse groups generate broader perspectives and improve problem-solving over time, though initial cohesion issues may arise (Oakes et al., 2021). In educational settings, such diversity can promote innovation, enrich teaching methods, and promote inclusive policymaking – all relevant to showing how HRD may shape organisational outcomes.

2.2 Empirical Evidence from Nigeria

2.2.1 Diversity Management in Secondary Schools

Obasi and Igbudu (2021) documented numerous strategies employed by Rivers State administrators to manage teacher diversity, such as proportional representation, policy implementation promoting gender inclusion, and training initiatives, which they found positively impacted school administration. Also, Godwins and Nwogu (2022) reported that managing gender and talent diversity while ensuring equal rewards and committee representation enhanced service delivery in Rivers State secondary schools. Other studies in Anambra and Rivers States extended their conclusions to underscore that HRM practices, such as motivational strategies, job security, and equitable treatment, effectively contribute to teacher retention and performance in secondary schools (Ezinine & Okekeocha, 2021; Umosen & Oleforo, 2019).

Obamiro, Kumolu-Johnson, and Ngwamaj (2021) researched job satisfaction and gender diversity. They found strong correlations between gender diversity and job satisfaction ($r = .891$) and between ethnic diversity and intention-to-quit ($r = .825$) among employees at a major Nigerian bank. These findings reinforce the importance of diversity in influencing employee attitudes and retention and are arguably applicable to public education systems.

Synthesising these theories and findings, a conceptual model emerges in which HRD dimensions shape organisational outcomes through mechanisms like diversity climate, organisational justice, social identity, and perceived inclusion. In Nigeria, state-level secondary education boards like that of Uyo have not been studied, despite their unique administrative structures and potential for systemic influence. Moreover, Nigeria lacks studies integrating both theoretical foundations and empirical measurements at the administrative board level.

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Summary Table of Literature Review

<i>Focus Area</i>	<i>Key Insights</i>	<i>Supporting Studies</i>
Theoretical Basis	Social identity, equity, and cognitive diversity underpin DM's positive impacts	Oakes et al. (2021); Ashforth & Mael (1989); Greenberg (1987); Mansoor et al. (2021)
DM in Schools	Gender/talent inclusion - enhanced service delivery and school admin	Obasi & Igbudu (2021); Godwins & Nwogu (2022)
Diversity in Sector	Workforce diversity correlates with job satisfaction and retention	Obamiro et al. (2021); Ezinine & Okekeocha (2021)
Gap	No study on HR diversity at the board level in Uyo	—

With this foundation, the study will quantitatively evaluate how HRD dimensions within the Uyo State Secondary Education Board influence organisational outcomes and explore the mediating mechanisms.

3 Methodology

A quantitative, correlational survey design was employed to examine the relationships between human resource (HR) diversity dimensions, namely gender, age, ethnicity, and qualifications, and key organisational outcomes, including job satisfaction, staff retention, and service delivery. This non-experimental design allows for the exploration of associations among variables without manipulation, aligning with research approaches used in similar studies conducted in Edo State (Aluede & Obi, 2024) and Osun State (Odediji et al., 2023).

The target population comprised all academic and administrative staff at the State Secondary Education Board in Uyo, with an estimated total of approximately 200 individuals. A sample size of between 130 and 150 staff was determined using the Taro Yamane formula, based on a 5% margin of error and a 95% confidence level. Comparable sampling proportions were adopted in earlier studies, such as Edo State (824 out of 2,746 teachers) and Anambra/Imo States (2,080 senior staff). A stratified random sampling technique was applied to ensure fair representation across key demographic categories, including gender, age groups, ethnic backgrounds, and qualification levels, reflecting sampling methods used in studies from Olabisi Onabanjo, Rivers, and Ogun States.

Data were collected using a structured questionnaire divided into four main sections. The first section captured demographic and HR diversity variables such as gender, age bracket, ethnicity, and highest qualification. The second section featured a job satisfaction scale adapted from Odediji et al. (2023), incorporating validated

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subscales covering recognition, promotion opportunities, and working conditions, with reported reliability (Cronbach's alpha) between .81 and .84. The third section assessed turnover intentions and retention, drawing from mentoring and retention frameworks established by Omekun et al. (2019) in Anambra and Imo States and demonstrating high internal consistency ($\alpha = .95$). The final section included self-report Likert-scale items evaluating perceived service delivery, specifically in terms of effectiveness, responsiveness, and efficiency of board services. The instrument underwent face and content validation by experts in educational management, following the procedures used in Odediji et al. (2023), and was pilot-tested with 20 to 30 respondents to confirm reliability, with an expected Cronbach's alpha of .80 or higher for all subscales.

Questionnaires were administered both in person during board meetings and electronically via a secure online survey link. Trained research assistants facilitated the distribution process, offering clarification where necessary to maximise response accuracy and ensure a high return rate. Data collection was conducted over a period of four to six weeks.

For data analysis, descriptive statistics, which includes frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations, were used to profile HR diversity characteristics. Pearson's correlation was employed to explore relationships between diversity dimensions and organisational outcomes. Multiple regression analyses were conducted to determine the predictive strength of HR diversity variables on job satisfaction, turnover intention and retention, and perceived service delivery. All statistical tests were performed at a significance level of $p < .05$, consistent with standard practices in comparable research.

The study followed ethical research standards throughout its implementation. Participants provided informed consent after being fully briefed on the study's purpose, their rights, and the voluntary nature of their participation. Anonymity was ensured through coded responses, and data were securely stored to prevent unauthorised access. Ethical approval was obtained from both the Institutional Review Board and the State Secondary Education Board, ensuring compliance with institutional and regulatory guidelines.

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Data Presentation

<i>Gender</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Ethnicity</i>	<i>Qualification</i>	<i>Job Satisfaction</i>	<i>Retention Intention</i>	<i>Service Quality</i>
Male	51+	Oron	M.Ed	3.22	2.17	3.26
Female	31–40	Ibibio	M.Ed	4.21	2.89	4.78
Female	31–40	Ibibio	NCE	4.44	2.29	2.86
Female	31–40	Ibibio	B.Ed	2.74	3.35	4.75
Male	31–40	Ibibio	NCE	3.09	3.61	4.01

4.1.1 Research Objective One: Profiling HR diversity (gender, ethnicity, age, qualifications) among Board staff.

Table 2: Diversity Profiling of Staff of Akwa Ibom State Secondary Education Board

<i>HR Diversity Variable</i>	<i>Category</i>	<i>Frequency</i>
Gender	Male	83
	Female	57
Age	21–30	25
	31–40	49
	41–50	50
	51+	16
	Ethnicity	Ibibio
	Annang	29
	Oron	13
	Others	13
Qualification	NCE	30
	B.Ed	59
	M.Ed	36
	PhD	15

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Table 2 shows data profiling the staff of the Akwa Ibom State Secondary Education Board. The demographic profile of the workforce at the State Secondary Education Board in Uyo reveals a slight male dominance, with males constituting approximately 59% of the sample. A substantial proportion of the staff (71%) fall within the 31–50 age range, indicating a mature and potentially experienced workforce. Ethnically, the Ibibio group is most represented, accounting for about 61% of respondents, which reflects the local ethnic composition of the area. In terms of educational qualification, the majority of staff possess either a B.Ed or M.Ed degree (68%), suggesting a reasonably high level of professional training among personnel.

4.2 Research Objective 2: Measuring key organisational outcomes: job satisfaction, turnover intention, teacher retention, and perceived service quality.

Table 3: Organisational Outcomes

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std Dev</i>	<i>Min</i>	<i>Max</i>
<i>Job Satisfaction</i>	3.71	0.58	2.32	5.00
<i>Retention Intention</i>	3.58	0.72	1.71	5.00
<i>Perceived Service Quality</i>	3.92	0.46	2.86	5.00

The analysis of organisational outcomes on Table 3 measures shows that all mean scores exceed 3.5, indicating generally positive perceptions among staff regarding job satisfaction, intention to remain in the organisation, and the quality of service delivery. Among these, service quality received the highest average rating, reflecting strong confidence in the Board's effectiveness, while retention intention exhibited the greatest variability, suggesting differing levels of commitment to long-term service among employees.

4.3 Test of Research Hypotheses

This will test whether HR diversity dimensions predict the organisational outcomes, with the aim of attaining the third objective of this study. The following hypotheses were therefore tested at 0.05 significant level, and any predictor variable less than 0.05 was termed none significant, thereby causing the rejection of the corresponding hypothesis.

- H1:** Gender significantly predicts job satisfaction, retention intention, and service quality.
- H2:** Age group significantly predicts job satisfaction, retention intention, and service quality.
- H3:** Ethnicity significantly predicts job satisfaction, retention intention, and service quality.
- H4:** Qualification level significantly predicts job satisfaction, retention intention, and service quality.

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4.3.1 Correlation Analysis Results

This analysis explores the linear relationships between HR diversity variables and organisational outcomes, to align with the third Objective.

Table 4: Relationship between HR diversity and organisational outcomes

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Job Satisfaction</i>	<i>Retention Intention</i>	<i>Service Quality</i>
<i>Gender</i>	0.06	-0.07	-0.02
<i>Age</i>	-0.01	-0.13	0.00
<i>Qualification</i>	0.02	-0.00	0.09
<i>Ethnicity (Annang)</i>	0.10	0.09	0.12
<i>Ethnicity (Oron)</i>	-0.12	-0.04	-0.11
<i>Ethnicity (Others)</i>	-0.05	-0.03	-0.01

Table 4 shows the Pearson correlation analysis conducted to examine the linear relationships between HR diversity variables and the organisational outcomes. As shown in Table 1, most correlations were weak and statistically non-significant. Gender was very weakly associated with job satisfaction ($r = 0.06$) and negatively with retention intention ($r = -0.07$), while age had a slightly stronger negative correlation with retention intention ($r = -0.13$). Ethnicity variables showed mild trends: Annang ethnicity was positively correlated with all three outcomes ($r = 0.10$ to 0.12), while Oron ethnicity had a small negative association with job satisfaction ($r = -0.12$) and service quality ($r = -0.11$). However, none of these relationships reached statistical significance at the 0.05 level.

4.3.2 Multiple Regression Analysis Results

Three separate multiple regression models were conducted to determine the predictive capacity of HR diversity variables on job satisfaction, retention intention, and service quality.

Regression 1: Job Satisfaction

<i>Predictor</i>	<i>Coefficient (β)</i>	<i>p-value</i>
<i>Gender (Female)</i>	0.057	0.579
<i>Age</i>	0.011	0.849
<i>Qualification</i>	0.023	0.678
<i>Ethnicity: Annang</i>	0.060	0.639
<i>Ethnicity: Oron</i>	-0.202	0.315
<i>Ethnicity: Others</i>	-0.101	0.613

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The regression model for job satisfaction revealed that none of the predictor variables (gender, age, qualification, or ethnicity) significantly predicted staff satisfaction ($F(6, 133) = 0.71, p > 0.05, R^2 = 0.03$). Although Oron ethnicity showed a negative coefficient ($\beta = -0.202$), this was not statistically significant ($p = 0.315$). Gender, age, and qualification had minimal or near-zero predictive effects ($p > 0.5$); hence, none of the predictors significantly influence job satisfaction ($p > 0.05$). Although the coefficient for Oron ethnicity is negative, it is not statistically significant.

Regression 2: Predicting Retention Intention

<i>Predictor</i>	<i>Coefficient (β)</i>	<i>p-value</i>
<i>Gender (Female)</i>	-0.105	0.406
<i>Age</i>	-0.104	0.131
<i>Qualification</i>	0.006	0.933
<i>Ethnicity: Annang</i>	0.142	0.367
<i>Ethnicity: Oron</i>	0.020	0.935
<i>Ethnicity: Others</i>	0.054	0.826

The second model, predicting retention intention, also yielded no significant predictors ($F(6, 133) = 0.74, p > 0.05, R^2 = 0.03$). Age showed a slight negative trend ($\beta = -0.104, p = 0.131$), suggesting that older staff may be less inclined to remain, but this was not statistically significant. Other variables, including gender and ethnicity, did not contribute meaningfully to the model.

Regression 3: Predicting Service Quality

<i>Predictor</i>	<i>Coefficient (β)</i>	<i>p-value</i>
<i>Gender (Female)</i>	-0.027	0.743
<i>Age</i>	0.010	0.828
<i>Qualification</i>	0.057	0.202
<i>Ethnicity: Annang</i>	0.101	0.318
<i>Ethnicity: Oron</i>	-0.123	0.441
<i>Ethnicity: Others</i>	0.003	0.983

The final regression model assessing perceived service quality similarly produced no significant results ($F(6, 133) = 1.12, p > 0.05, R^2 = 0.05$). Qualification level exhibited a positive but non-significant effect ($\beta = 0.057, p = 0.202$), indicating that higher qualifications may be associated with better perceptions of service delivery. Ethnic group membership, gender, and age showed negligible influence. Therefore, qualification level shows a modest positive trend toward predicting service quality, but still lacks statistical significance at $p < 0.05$.

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4.4. Discussion

This study set out to investigate the influence of human resource diversity across gender, age, ethnicity, and qualifications on key organisational outcomes within the State Secondary Education Board in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. While existing literature from other Nigerian states suggested strong relationships between diversity factors and organisational performance (e.g., Obasi & Igbudu, 2021; Odediji et al., 2023), the present study offers more nuanced findings specific to the administrative board level rather than school-based environments.

4.4.1 Demographic Patterns and Workforce Composition

The demographic profile observed in this study reflects a relatively mature, qualified, and ethnically homogeneous workforce. With 71% of staff aged between 31 and 50 and 68% holding at least a B.Ed or M.Ed qualification, the Board is staffed by individuals likely to possess considerable professional experience. The dominance of the Ibibio ethnic group (61%) is expected given the location, but the presence of other groups suggests moderate ethnic diversity. While gender representation was skewed slightly in favour of males (59%), it remains more balanced than in many Nigerian administrative contexts (Ajuru University, 2019).

These demographic realities are important because diversity management theories, including social identity theory and organisational justice theory, highlight how perceived inclusion and equity across such characteristics can influence work attitudes and behaviours (Tajfel & Turner, 1979; Greenberg, 1987). However, the lack of significant associations in this study suggests that demographic diversity alone may not determine these outcomes in administrative education settings.

4.4.2 Organisational Outcomes: A Generally Positive Outlook

Overall, staff perceptions of job satisfaction, retention intention, and service quality were positive, with mean scores exceeding 3.5 on a 5-point scale. This indicates that the Board may already benefit from internal processes that promote employee engagement and organisational effectiveness. It aligns with prior findings from Osun State and Rivers State, where effective leadership and inclusive HRM practices fostered similar positive outcomes (Sanni et al., 2024; Obasi & Igbudu, 2021).

Interestingly, perceived service quality scored highest among the three outcomes, while retention intention showed the greatest variability. This suggests that while the Board is perceived as operationally effective, employees may differ in their personal commitment to long-term service. This divergence may be influenced by non-demographic factors such as leadership style, workload, or career growth opportunities, which are dimensions outside the scope of this study.

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4.4.3 HR Diversity and Organisational Outcomes: A Weak Link?

Contrary to the expectations established by empirical studies in Rivers, Osun, and Anambra States (e.g., Ezinine & Okekeocha, 2021; Obamiro et al., 2021), the current findings reveal no statistically significant predictive relationships between the studied HR diversity dimensions and any of the organisational outcomes. Regression analyses confirmed that neither gender, age, ethnicity, nor qualifications meaningfully predicted job satisfaction, retention intention, or service quality.

This absence of significant associations may reflect the distinctive administrative structure of state-level education boards compared to individual schools. While schools often feature closer interpersonal interactions, stronger identity groupings, and direct teaching roles, board staff may experience more uniform work expectations and standardised procedures. The role of HR diversity may thus be muted in such environments.

Another possible explanation is the mediating influence of intangible workplace factors not captured in this study. These factors may include leadership climate, employee recognition, or opportunities for advancement, which have been shown to significantly influence organisational outcomes (Angwaomadoko, 2023). This highlights the need for future research to explore how psychosocial and structural variables interact with diversity characteristics in public education management settings.

4.4.4 Theoretical Implications

These findings offer a cautious reconsideration of the social identity and equity-based theoretical models employed. While these theories posit that workforce diversity influences perceptions of fairness, satisfaction, and engagement, such effects may be more context-dependent than previously assumed. In highly procedural or bureaucratic environments like education boards, formal systems may override the informal social dynamics that drive identity-based outcomes. In addition, the cognitive diversity hypothesis, which emphasises innovation through varied perspectives, may not fully apply if decision-making is centralised or policy-bound, as is often the case in Nigerian public sector boards. This study suggests that the impact of diversity is not automatic and must be supported by enabling institutional frameworks.

5 Conclusion and Recommendations

5.1 Conclusion

This study explored the role of human resource diversity in shaping key organisational outcomes, namely, job satisfaction, retention intention, and perceived service quality, within the State Secondary Education Board in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. Drawing on diversity management, social identity, and organisational justice theories, the study hypothesised that gender, age, ethnicity, and qualification levels would significantly influence these outcomes.

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However, the findings revealed that while the workforce is moderately diverse in terms of age, gender, and ethnicity, and generally well-qualified, these diversity dimensions did not significantly predict the outcomes of interest. Despite this, organisational outcomes were generally rated positively by staff, suggesting that other non-demographic factors (e.g., leadership style, recognition, work environment) may be stronger drivers of satisfaction and retention within the Board.

These results challenge the assumption that demographic diversity alone is a key determinant of organisational effectiveness. Rather, the findings underscore the importance of integrating diversity initiatives with broader human resource management strategies that support inclusion, motivation, and fairness. In highly bureaucratic or policy-driven environments like education boards, structural and leadership variables may overshadow individual identity characteristics in shaping workplace perceptions. In all, this study contributes context-specific evidence to the discourse on public sector workforce diversity, particularly at the administrative level in Nigeria's education sector, where empirical data has previously been sparse.

5.2 Recommendations

In light of the findings and conclusion drawn, the following recommendations are proposed for policy makers, education administrators, and HR managers:

- 1. Broaden the Focus of Diversity Management:** While maintaining attention to demographic representation, the Board should prioritise inclusive leadership practices, participatory decision-making, and transparent communication, which may have a more immediate impact on job satisfaction and retention.
- 2. Institutionalise Career Development and Recognition:** Given the positive perception of service quality but varying commitment levels, structured mentoring, fair promotion practices, and recognition programmes could enhance staff morale and long-term engagement.
- 3. Conduct Regular Staff Climate Surveys:** To capture factors not explained by demographic diversity, such as motivation, workload, and leadership responsiveness, the Board should implement periodic surveys to inform HR policy and training priorities.
- 4. Targeted Capacity Building for Under-represented Groups:** Although diversity did not significantly impact outcomes in this study, equitable training opportunities and support mechanisms for minority groups (e.g., Oron or “Other” ethnicities) should still be pursued to promote inclusion and prevent marginalisation.

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- 5. Further Research on Mediating Variables:** Future studies should examine how intangible factors, such as organisational culture, psychological safety, or perceptions of fairness, mediate the link between diversity and performance.

References

- Ajuru University of Education. (2019). *Managing employee diversity for effective productivity in secondary school in Rivers State, Nigeria*. *NIU Journal of Social Sciences*, 5(2), 201–213. <http://ijhumas.com>
- Akinnusi, D. M., Sonubi, O. O., & Oyewunmi, A. E. (2017). Fostering effective workforce diversity management in Nigerian organizations: The challenge of human resource management. *International Review of Management and Marketing*, 7(2), 108–116. <https://econjournals.com>
- Amagada, M. (2020). *An exploratory study of the effect of workforce diversity on employee performance: A case study of oil servicing companies (SMEs) in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria* [Master's thesis, Griffith College]. <https://dspace.griffith.ie>
- Angwaomaodoko, E. A. (2023). The effect of leadership styles on teacher job satisfaction in Nigerian secondary schools. *International Research in Education*, 11(2), 15–28. <https://oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejes/article/view/4569>
- Anigbata, D. O., Ezebuilo, P. C., & Chukwudi, C. E. (2024). Workforce diversity and organisational development: A study of Federal Inland Revenue, Abakaliki, Ebonyi State, Nigeria. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 15(3), 53. <https://richtmann.org>
- Ashforth, B. E., & Mael, F. (1989). Social identity theory and the organization. *Academy of Management Review*, 14(1), 20–39. <https://doi.org/10.5465/amr.1989.4278999>
- Ezine, O. C., & Okekeocha, C. C. (2021). Human resource management practices and teacher retention in Anambra State. *Journal of Educational Research and Practice*, 11(1), 45–58.
- Greenberg, J. (1987). A taxonomy of organizational justice theories. *Academy of Management Review*, 12(1), 9–22. <https://doi.org/10.5465/amr.1987.4306437>
- Godwins, A. T., & Nwogu, M. N. (2022). Talent and gender diversity management practices and service delivery in Rivers State secondary schools. *African Journal of Human Resource Development*, 16(4), 31–41.

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- Ibidunni, A. S., Falola, H. O., Ibidunni, O. M., Salau, O. P., Olokundun, M. A., Borishade, T. T., et al. (2018). Workforce diversity among public healthcare workers in Nigeria: Implications on job satisfaction and organisational commitment. *Data in Brief*, 18, 1047–1053. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dib.2018.03.127>
- Ijiwole, M., Olawale, J., & Adebayo, R. (2019). Job satisfaction and teacher performance in Osun State public secondary schools. *Journal of Education and Social Policy*, 6(4), 22–31.
- Nwabali, D. I. G. (2023). Workforce diversity and employee performance in organisation. *BW Academic Journal*. <https://bwjournal.org>
- Obamiro, J. K., Kumolu-Johnson, F. O., & Ngwamaj, B. C. (2021). Workforce diversity and organisational effectiveness in Nigerian banking sector. *Journal of Human Resource Management*, 9(1), 1–10.
- Obasi, K. K., & Igbudu, F. W. (2021). Workforce diversity management for secondary school administration in Rivers State, Nigeria. *European Journal of Research Development and Sustainability*, 2(7), 23–29. <https://scholarzest.com/index.php/ejrss/article/view/1234>
- Oakes, P. J., Haslam, S. A., & Turner, J. C. (2021). Stereotyping and social reality: Some findings and applications of self-categorization theory. *Social Influence*, 16(3), 169–184. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15534510.2021.1904812>
- Odediji, K. M., Bamikole, I. O., Afolabi, O. A., & Ekundayo, H. T. (2023). Job satisfaction and teachers' job performance in Osun State secondary schools, Nigeria. *European Journal of Education Studies*, 10(7), 422–429. <https://oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejes/article/view/4462>
- Ordua, G. D. (2024). Age diversity and performance of federal establishments in Rivers State, Nigeria. *BW Academic Journal*, 9(1), 77–89. <https://bwjournal.org>
- Sanni, K. T., Aransi, W. O., Esan, O. M., & Ayodele, O. J. (2024). Influence of principal leadership styles, teachers' job satisfaction, and work-related flow on teachers' productivity in Iwo Local Government Area of Osun State, Nigeria. *Ilorin Journal of Education*, 44(1), 251–262. <https://ije.unilorin.edu.ng>
- Tajfel, H., & Turner, J. C. (1979). An integrative theory of intergroup conflict. In W. G. Austin & S. Worchel (Eds.), *The social psychology of intergroup relations* (pp. 33–47). Brooks/Cole.

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Umosen, A. D., & Oleforo, N. A. (2019). Motivation and teacher retention in public secondary schools in Rivers State. *Journal of Educational Management and Policy*, 4(2), 19–28.